

Australian Citizen Science Association

Annual Report
2021-2022

Acknowledgement of Country

The Australian Citizen Science Association acknowledges the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples of this nation. We pay our respects to ancestors and Elders, past and present and recognise their unique cultural and spiritual relationships to the land, waters, and seas, as well as their rich contribution to society and citizen science.

The Australian Citizen Science Association Annual Report 2021-2022 is published by the Australian Citizen Science Association Inc. (ACSA)
c/o Faculty of Science, University of Sydney NSW, 2006 Australia.

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Cover image: Hervé Sauquet is taking a picture of horse dung fungus (*Pisolithus arhizus*) using the iNaturalist application, during a Big Bushfire Bioblitz at North Brother Mountain in Dooragan National Park. The photograph was taken by Peter Crowcroft.

Compiled by Jessie Oliver with support from Lisa Evans and Annie Lane

Cite as: Australian Citizen Science Association. (2022). Australian Citizen Science Association Annual Report 2021/2022. 1-39. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7408432>

Chair's Report

2021-2022 has been another eventful year for the Australian Citizen Science Association (ACSA) and it's been an uplifting year for citizen science in many ways. We know that participation rates spiked during the Covid lockdowns and citizen science is often in the media, usually as a good news story. It's also being increasingly valued by governments and researchers.

ACSA has been involved in a plethora of activities over the year. You'll find details in section 3 of this report but the following are selected highlights:

- advocated for commitment to citizen science in strategy, policy and planning. The Commonwealth's Threatened Species Action Plan and the UNESCO Recommendation on open science are recent examples.
- delivered a highly successful online conference CitSciOz21 comprising interactive symposia and workshops, pre-recorded talks and keynote presentations;
- awarded another two SEED grants;
- supported our members by promoting their work on ACSA social media platforms and providing advice on the design and implementation of citizen science initiatives;
- fostered participation in citizen science at state and territory levels through numerous events such as science festivals, trainings, field events and seminars;
- partnered with the University of NSW, Minderoo, Atlas of Living Australia and the now Department for Climate Change, Energy, Environment and Water to track the recovery of ecosystems from the 2019-20 bushfires; and
- developed a citizen science strategy for the NSW Biodiversity Conservation Trust.

ACSA went through some major changes in personnel during the year. Dr Erin Roger stepped down as chair and Dr Geoff Garrett relinquished his role as ACSA patron at the 2021 AGM. Erin led the evolution of ACSA from its infancy to the strong and confident Association it is today. Geoff served as ACSA's patron since February 2018, provided sound and wise advice, and helped ACSA expand its networks and spread its influence. Thank you Erin and Geoff for your commitment to ACSA and many years of service. Thanks also to outgoing members of the ACSA Management Committee. Your contributions are deeply appreciated.

ACSA's National Coordinator, Amy Slocombe, finished with ACSA in July 2022, and her unwavering commitment to ACSA needs to be acknowledged before another year passes. Amy started with ACSA in 2016 and was instrumental in shaping ACSA and growing support for citizen science. It was a pleasure to work with you Amy. Thank you!

Thank you also to ACSA's volunteer management committee, chapter leaders, and other citizen science champions for your help in steering ACSA in the right direction. Finally, thanks to you, wonderful members, for your support of ACSA and enthusiasm for citizen science. I'm feeling very positive about where citizen science is heading and it promises to be another exciting and busy year ahead.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in grey ink that reads "Annie Lane". The signature is fluid and cursive, with a large initial 'A'.

Annie Lane

ACSA Chair

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Section 1 - An Overview of the Association

About Us

The Australian Citizen Science Association (ACSA) is the peak body for citizen science in Australia. ACSA was first conceived in 2014 when a large number of dedicated volunteers came together to discuss how to increase awareness and support of Australian citizen science both nationally and globally. The Association describes citizen science as a form of science involving public participation and collaboration in scientific inquiries with the aim to increase scientific knowledge.

Our Mission

A community that supports, informs, and develops citizen science.

Our Vision

To advance citizen science through sharing of knowledge, collaboration, capacity building & advocacy.

Our Goals

The Australian Citizen Science Association actively works to:

- Encourage and promote broad and meaningful participation in citizen science.
- Facilitate inclusive and collaborative partnerships.
- Support the development of tools and resources that further best practices.
- Ensure the value and impact of citizen science and its outputs are realised.
- Establish ACSA as an effective, trusted and well-recognised organisation and hub for citizen science in Australia.

Our People

During the reporting period, one patron resigned and another was appointed. Additionally, the Management Committee included four office bearers (i.e. Chair, Vice Chair, Secretary, and Treasurer), as well as two to four general members, and a representative University of Sydney as the ACSA host institution. The ACSA Management Committee was supported by its International Liaison, a Citizen Science Global Partnership Liaison, and a Social Media Moderator, all of whom are appointed to these roles based on expertise in their fields. The day-to-day operations of ACSA were conducted by a National Coordinator who was employed part-time.

Our People

Patrons

Hugh Possingham
Appointed 05 Nov 21

Geoff Garrett
Resigned 29 Oct 21

Management Committee

Annie Lane
Chair
Term began
29 Oct 2021

Erin Roger
Chair
Term ended
29 Oct 2021

Stephanie von Gavel
Vice Chair
In the role the whole
financial year

Peter Runcie
Treasurer
In the role the whole
financial year

Bill Flynn
General Member &
became Secretary on
06 Feb 2022

Alysoun Boyle
Secretary
Resigned
06 Feb 2022

Darryl Ebenezer
Gen member & Chap.
Vice Chair - QLD;
Began 29 Oct 21

James Chong
General member
Term began
29 Oct 2021

Jock Mackenzie
General member
Term began
29 Oct 2021

Leigh Stitz
General member
Term began
29 Oct 2021

Lisa Evans
General member
In the role the whole
financial year

Steve Turton
General member
Term began
29 Oct 2021

Cobi Calyx
General member
Term ended
29 Oct 2021

Jenn Loder
General member
Term ended
29 Oct 2021

Maxine Newlands
General member
Term ended
29 Oct 2021

Management Committee continued

Rosalinde Brinkman
General member
Term ended
29 Oct 2021

Alice Motion
Host Representative
In the role the whole
financial year

Employee

Amy Slocombe
National Coordinator
In the role the whole
financial year

Volunteers

Michelle Neil
Social Media
Moderator; In the role
the full financial year

Libby Hepburn
CSGP Liaison
In the role the whole
financial year

Jessie Oliver
International Liaison
In the role the whole
financial year

John Pring
Chapter Chair - ACT,
Resigned 31 Dec 2021

Janine Bedros
Chapter Chair - QLD
In the role the whole
financial year

Luise Manning
Chapter Secretary -
QLD; In the role the
full financial year

Sylvia Clarke
Chapter Chair - SA
In the role the whole
financial year

Katie Irvine
Chapter Vice Chair -
SA; In the role the
whole financial year

Tahlia Perry
Chapter
Secretary - SA
Resigned 23 Feb 22

Isabella Wilson
Chapter
Secretary - SA
Term began 23 Feb 22

Kade Mills
Chapter Chair - VIC
In the role the whole
financial year

Tess Hayes
Chapter Vice Chair -
VIC; In the role the
whole financial year

Yvonne Cabuang
Chapter Secretary -
VIC; In the role the
whole financial year

Alex Chapman
Chapter Chair &
Secretary - WA
Term began
23 Oct 2021

Marnie Giroud
Chapter Vice
Chair - WA
Term began
23 Oct 2021

Section 2 - Governance

Our Organisation

The Australian Citizen Science Association was registered as an incorporated association (Registration No. A 05747) via Registrar-General's Office in the Australian Capital Territory in June 2016, and began following regulations upheld by Access Canberra. A year later, the Australian Citizen Science Association Incorporated (ACSA) registered to be an Australian Registered Body (ARB No. 618 948 271) with Australian Securities & Investment Commission (ASIC). This allows the Association to conduct business throughout all states and territories within Australia. In July 2018, ACSA was certified as a registered small charity with the Australian Charities and Not-for-profits Commission (ACNC).

The Association is governed by a constitution that sets out the high-level objectives, powers and administrative arrangements, in accordance with the Associations Incorporation Act 1991 and regulations set by the above-mentioned bodies.

Our Management Committee

The Association is led by a volunteer Management Committee (MC). The MC consists of a Chair, Vice Chair, Secretary, and Treasurer, as well as at least two general members. Members of the MC are elected by ACSA members at the Annual General Meeting for a two-year term, and MC members can opt to nominate for additional terms. Additionally, the MC includes a representative from the host organisation of ACSA, which is currently the University of Sydney. Collectively, ACSA Management Committee members have knowledge or experience in areas such as citizen science, science, business, finance, stakeholder engagement, and fundraising.

Our Sub-Committees

Sub-committees are formed to advance the implementation of the ACSA strategic plan. These sub-committees provide advice and make recommendations to the MC. Membership of sub-committees consists of MC members, broader volunteers, and staff with expertise, interest, and sometimes responsibilities in the subject area. During 2021-2022, three sub-committees met regularly: 1. Governance and Advocacy; 2. Finance; and 3. Membership, Engagement and Communications.

Our Broader Leadership Roles

ACSA also has a number of individual members who act on behalf of ACSA in specific volunteer roles created to advance the organisational mission. For instance, the ACSA MC has appointed the specialist roles of ACSA Patron, ACSA Social Media Moderator, ACSA International Liaison, and Citizen Science Global Partnership (CSGP) Liaison.

Our State and Territory Chapters

ACSA Regional Chapters promote ACSA and citizen science through diverse community engagement activities (see the Our Objectives and Achievements section for an overview). Chapter Chairs attend Management Committee meetings to relay national and chapter information back and forth. Chapters follow [ACSA Chapter Protocols](#) set forth by the MC. However, they are self-organised and make their own governance and operational arrangements.

Our Employees

Since October 2016, ACSA has had one part-time employee who supports the MC by carrying out operational activities. The Association engages additional short-term staff or contractors on an as-needed basis to support large-scale ACSA event organisation (e.g. national conferences), ACSA consulting contracts, and other operational activities.

Our Consulting

In addition to membership subscriptions, revenue is generated through ACSA Consulting from June 2021. Proceeds of our consulting services work are used to advance citizen science in Australia. ACSA Consulting offers services such as:

- Citizen Science Strategy Development and Implementation
- Citizen Science Project Design, Management and Evaluation
- Best Practice Citizen Science Advice
- Citizen Science Technology Design
- Capacity Building Workshops (Project Management and Evaluation)
- Keynote Addresses

Our Membership Structure

In the 2017-2018 financial year, a financial membership structure was introduced for ACSA, as a step towards ensuring the Association became a self-sustaining organisation.

Membership types and fees per annum during the 2021-2022 financial year were:

- **Individual** - subscribe an individual person at a full rate: \$80
- **Concession** - subscribe a student, senior (60+), pensioner, or veteran: \$40
- **Organisational** - subscribe up to 5 members: \$350
- **Corporate** - subscribe 6 to 15 members: \$860

At the start of the 2021-2022 financial year, the ACSA membership structure changed in several ways. The organisation originally had annual rolling memberships, with renewal dates based on the date of purchase. Members can now also automatically renew subscriptions annually. Given the projected growth of ACSA, the Association became registered for Goods and Services Tax (GST), as of 1 July 2021. To keep up with higher operating expenses and 10% GST, subscription fees were increased from the previous year. The prices listed above are GST-inclusive.

Section 3 - Our Objectives & Achievements

ACSA exists to represent citizen science at local, national, and international levels, as well as to actively advocate for the inclusion of citizen science in policy and practice. The ACSA operational objectives are to:

- Raise the profile of citizen science and ACSA through advocacy and outreach
- Deliver value for members
- Be financially secure to allow us to conduct impactful work
- Apply good governance practices to ensure we are working effectively and transparently

In addition to the conference, ACSA leadership undertook a variety of advocacy, consultation, liaison, and partnership activities to grow and strengthen citizen science. In accordance with our [3-year ACSA strategic plan](#), we continued to grow citizen science diverse actions relating to participation, partnerships, practices, and platform.

Fostering Participation

During the 2021-2022 financial year, fostered participation in citizen science through diverse activities, including but not limited to:

- Delivering our biggest event of the year, another Australian Citizen Science Association conference referred to as #CitSciOz21. In keeping with Covid-19 times, we pivoted to host a completely online event that ran from October 27th to 29th, 2021. The conference was a huge success. Almost 200 delegates were able to enjoy seven interactive workshops, seven live symposia, almost 50 pre-recorded talks, a special presentation about international citizen science projects, and five inspiring keynotes. The wealth of content spanned topics such as recovery from bushfires, protecting waterways, monitoring the Great Barrier Reef, open science, data sharing, technology, adaptive sampling, education, health, collaboration and much more. The feedback was overwhelmingly positive. Nearly all conference talks can be watched via the [ACSA Youtube Channel](#). Thank you to the volunteer conference committee for pulling off a successful conference and in particular Lisa Evans who was our conference champion.

Promotion for the CitSciOz21 online conference, including our keynote speakers

- Exchanging information across the citizen science community through our active social media presence. Our longest and strongest social media presence has continued to be via Twitter and Facebook platforms, though our newer channels on Instagram, LinkedIn, and Youtube continue to steadily increase as well.

The total number of followers per platform by the end of the 2021-2022 financial year:

- Providing a local voice and representation through ACSA Regional Chapters while connecting directly to ACSA and citizen science at the national level. The ACSA Chapter for Western Australia (WA) was relaunched after a period of dormancy, and Chapters for the Australian Capital Territory and Region (ACT), Queensland (QLD), South Australia (SA), and Victoria (VIC) have all been active during the 2021-2022 financial year. Chapter groups participated in and hosted a wide variety of online and in-person opportunities for respective community members to network, learn about citizen science, and share the impacts of such scientific endeavours.

Example activities of ACSA Regional Chapters that took place during the 2021-2022 financial year:

Chapter	Date	Activity	Description
ACT	12 Aug 2021	Webinar	<p>FrogID: Informing frog conservation through citizen science with Nadiah Roslan</p>
ACT	17 Oct 2021	Webinar	<p><i>Great Southern BioBlitz</i> with host Libby Hepburn (Australia) and speakers Claudia Schipp (Australia), Bianca Darski (Brazil), Rupert Koopman (South Africa), and Michelle Neil (Australia)</p>
ACT	10 Feb 2022	Webinar	<p><i>The travels and home of the Latham's Snipe</i> with Lori Gould</p>
QLD	17 Jul-01 Aug 2021	Event	<p>Michelle Neil and Luise Manning at the 2021 Peaks to Points Festival</p>

Chapter	Date	Activity	Description
QLD	29-30 Aug 2021	Event	Dr. David Kopelke attended the World Science Festival's 2-day event in Gladstone on behalf of the ACSA QLD Chapter
QLD	30 Oct 2021	Event	An in-person Chapter meetup with Hugh Possingham
QLD	7-8 Nov 2021	Event	Luise Manning (Chapter Secretary) participated in the World Science Festival's 2-day event in Ipswich
QLD	23 Nov 2021	Event	Luise Manning presented to the Oxley Creek Catchment Association introducing citizen science and use of apps to help analyse water quality
QLD	20 Apr 2022	Webinar	<i>Observing Butterflies</i> with Helen Schwenke
QLD	19 Jun 2022	Event	Michelle Neil and Luise Manning attended the 2022 Sustainability and Science Showcase

Chapter	Date	Activity	Description
QLD	29-30 Aug 2021	Webinar	<p>Nature Exploration using iNaturalist with Thomas Mesaglio (thebeachcomber)</p>
SA	30 Oct 2021	Event	SA award finalists announced at Launch of National Science Week event
SA	7-8 Nov 2021	Event	ACSA-SA stall at Science Alive over 2 days
SA	23 Nov 2021	Event	SA Networking event to coincide with #CitSciOz22 at Edinburgh Hotel
SA	20 Apr 2022	Awards	<p>In early November, inaugural South Australian Citizen Science Awards were presented at the 2021 Tall Poppy and Unsung Hero of Science Award ceremony. The winners and finalists were featured again a few weeks later at the 2021 SA Science Excellence and Innovation Awards, helping to further raise the profile of citizen science.</p> <p>SA Citizen Science Awards 2021 Finalists and Winners Two categories included: <i>Science and Research Award</i> - Echidna CSI (winner) and Bryophyte Collection Transcription Project (finalist) <i>Engagement Award</i> - Kangaroo Island/ Victor Harbor Dolphin Watch (winner) and iBandi (finalist).</p>

Chapter	Date	Activity	Description
SA	30 Jun 2022	Meeting	First of series of meetings with DEW about \$2M SA citizen science fund
VIC	6 Jul 2021	Meeting	Participation in <i>Future of Citizen Science Forum</i> hosted by the Department of Environment, Water, Land and Planning
VIC	5 Aug 2021	Meeting	Second workshop to inform Victorian Citizen Science Strategy development
VIC	17 Apr 2022	Event	Representing ACSA-VIC for NGO Technical Advisory Group (TAG): Sharing guidelines for reviewing State of the Environment 2023 Expert Review (ongoing)
WA	23 Oct 2021	Chapter Launch	Re-launch of the Western Australia Chapter

Growing Partnerships

Additionally, we grew our partnerships through a range of collaborative and consulting endeavours during the 2021-2022 financial year, including:

- Exploring forest monitoring in late 2021 through [a pilot citizen science project called ForestEye](#), involving a partnership between ACSA, the NSW Natural Resources Commission, Atlas of Life in the Coastal Wilderness and the Bega Shire Valley Council. During the pilot program, members of the Bega Shire Valley community were provided invaluable opportunities to learn about forest monitoring, local plants and wildlife. Through the citizen science program, they also used technologies, such as motion-triggered camas and audio recorders, to explore processes for long-term monitoring of local forests.

A screenshot of the DigiVol platform that was used by participants to identify and tag animals in photographs that were captured by motion-detecting cameras as part of the Forest-Eye project.

- Partnering to deliver the [2022 Big Bushfire Bioblitz](#), with the University of New South Wales Centre for Ecosystem Science, the Atlas of Living Australia, Minderoo's Fire and Flood Resilience Initiative, and the former Department of Agriculture, Water and the Environment. The project included three bioblitzes in NSW in early 2022 to help track how our native ecosystems are recovering from the 2019-2020 bushfire season.

Nick Lambert preparing to photograph the patch of *Liparis reflexa* orchids. Hervé Sauquet is taking a picture of horse dung fungus (*Pisolithus arhizus*), during a Big Bushfire Bioblitz at North Brother Mountain in Dooragan National Park. The photograph was taken by Peter Crowcroft.

- Supporting Taronga Conservation Society Australia's 2022 [HATCH Accelerator Program](#) in May and June 2022 with the aim to inspire, support and launch innovative ideas to tackle some of our most pressing environmental and conservation challenges.
- Consulting activities also helped us advance our goals towards becoming a sustainable peak body. A key example for the 2021-2022 financial year included working with New South Wales Biodiversity Conservation Trust (BCT) to create their [statewide citizen science strategy](#).
- Delivering community-focused workshops another consulting example, which was aimed towards introducing residents of the Redlands City Council area to citizen science and collecting nature observations at IndigiScapes.

Empowering Practice

We set out, during the 2021-2022 financial year, to empower others with knowledge and resources to foster the growth of strong citizen science. Such activities included:

- Awarding another [two seed grants](#). One grant was awarded to the MYCommunity Applied Mycology project to fund the training of volunteers in taking herbarium specimens of fungi and the use of laboratory equipment and techniques related to environmental DNA. The second grant was awarded to 2 Bent Rods, which is a fishing school that will create videos & flyers to promote a free fishing app they have developed in partnership with industry experts.
- Leading conversations on the value of citizen science in Australia and internationally by coordinating and participating in a diverse array of webinars, conference panels, symposia, and workshops. For example, ACSA chair Annie Lane and Costa Georgiadis attended the Australian Biosecurity Symposium in May 2022, where citizen science was recognised as key to effective biosecurity surveillance and monitoring. Costa champions citizen science at every opportunity and is the Ambassador for the [Decade of Biosecurity](#).

ACSA Chair Annie Lane with Costa Georgiadis

Building a Platform (Advocacy)

We also advocated for the growth of citizen science as a valuable and inclusive approach to gaining knowledge about the world, which can inform actions to ensure a sustainable future. Such advocacy efforts included:

- Providing comments on the [Threatened Species Strategy Action Plan 2021 – 2026: Consultation Paper](#). Citizen Science is a key component of the Action Plan released in February 2022 by the Australian Government Department of Agriculture, Water and the Environment.
- Ensuring inclusion of citizen science in discussions around open science. Members of ACSA and the citizen science community globally worked to ensure that citizen science has a strong presence in the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), which was adopted by the General Conference of UNESCO at its 41st session, in November 2021. Members of the ACSA and international citizen science communities continue actively engaging with UNESCO working groups to steer the implementation of the recommendation.
- Guaranteeing citizen science is included in high-level discussions about how digital technologies can both advance and hinder an environmentally sustainable future. The UN Internet Governance Forum (IGF) is an annual event that brings people together from various stakeholder groups, as equals, to discuss such public policy issues that broadly relate to the Internet. In anticipation of the 2021 forum, a global multi-stakeholder group was formed, called Policy Network on Environment, to provide policy recommendations for equitable and environmentally sustainable use of digital information and communication technologies around the world. The Network members drafted a [publicly available report](#) and then presented content by teleconferencing at the IGF 2021. Members representing ACSA ensured that citizen science, open science, and strong data governance principles (i.e. FAIR and CARE principles) were an integral part of global recommendations.

Section 4 - Our Finances

Treasurer's Report

Financial Position

ACSA had \$183,154 in net assets (comprising assets and liabilities) as of 30 June 2022. Assets primarily consist of cash - \$140,702 and receivables owing - \$47,234. Cash increased from \$103,390 in the previous year. Retained earnings were \$183,154.

Financial Performance

For 2021-2022 financial year, ACSA achieved a net surplus of \$80,166 – a 67% increase over the previous year.

The improved financial performance was primarily due to increased consulting revenue and income from the online CitSciOz21 conference held 27 – 29 October 2021. We aim to have conferences once every two years and revenue fluctuates accordingly. Pleasingly, after a decline last year, membership fees and donations bounced back by 32% (from \$15,802 to \$20,855) to now exceed pre-pandemic levels (\$16,624 in the 2019-20 financial year).

Membership Subscription Types	Number of Members at 01 July 2021	Number of Members at 30 June 2022	Total number of members for any portion of 2021-2022
Concession	99	111	181
Individual	196	181	291
Organisational*	27	31	44
Corporate	0	0	0

*Note that the total number of Individual membership subscriptions includes both members who have independently purchased an individual subscription and people designated members under an organisational subscription (i.e. subscribing from 1 to 15 members per organisation).

Number of memberships per day during the 2021-2022 financial year

As with the previous year, ACSA received welcome government financial assistance via a JobSaver payment to help deal with the effects of COVID-19.

Although wage-related expenses decreased moderately there was an overall increase in expenditure mainly due to costs associated with paying consultants to deliver services.

The Future

Measures implemented in the previous year to reduce website-related expenses have paid off and we continue to explore ways to reduce non-staffing-related operational costs.

For the 2022-2023 financial year, we will continue to focus on income supporting the ongoing sustainability of the organisation, to add value to our members and Australian citizen science more broadly. If our application for Deductible Gift Recipient status is successful, we expect to actively focus on growing donation revenues.

On behalf of the ACSA Management Committee, I extend our gratitude to our staff, members, funding bodies, and clients for their essential financial and logistical support.

Peter Runcie

Treasurer

Section 5 - Acknowledgements and Thank You

Partners

Organisational Members

Organisational Members (continued)

Individual Members

Thank you to our members since our work is possible because of your passion for science and support for ACSA!

Volunteers

In addition to volunteers listed as Chapter office bearers in Section 1, thank you to several additional people for their contributions to chapter management and events.

- **ACT & Region Chapter:** Peter Brenton, Janet Anstee, Michael Mulvaney, Woo O'Reilly, and Stuart Harris
- **Queensland Chapter:** Caitlin Syme, Cherrie Bushnell, Cheryl Tan, and Jennifer Seevinck, and Michelle Neil
- **South Australia Chapter:** Alice Woodward, Craig Hughes, Craig Williams, Erinn Fagan-Jeffries, Jasmin Packer, Keri Hopeward, Michelle Blewitt, Michelle Clanahan, Robert Lawrence, Rosalie Lawrence, Rose Dow, Seamus Doherty, Sherry Pitman, Stephen Fricker, Steve Walker, and Tina Gillespie
- **Victoria Chapter:** Ann Borda, Christine Connelly, Julian O'Shea, Linden Ashcroft, Lynne Lucas, and Pat Bonney
- **Western Australia:** Claire Greenwell, Lisa Evans, and Tegan Douglas

The National Coordinator

Since October 2016, Amy Slocombe has worked tirelessly behind the scenes to keep ACSA operational, empowering each round of incoming Management Committee members, and keeping the community as a whole updated on citizen science happenings. Amy formally resigned as National Coordinator in July of 2022. However, to ensure a smooth transition, she has continued to show unparalleled support for ACSA by volunteering to continue assisting Jessie Oliver, Executive Officer, and Lisa Evans, Executive Support Officer, on an as-needed basis. From finance management to reporting obligations, her wealth of knowledge and continued dedication to ACSA cannot be acknowledged enough!

Amy with one of her farewell gifts, an Indigenous print inspired by the NAIDOC 2018 phrase "Because of her, we can"

Australian Citizen Science Association

Contact Us

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 www.youtube.com/c/AustralianCitizenScienceAssociation

Appendix A: Financial Statements

AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

INCOME AND EXPENDITURE STATEMENT FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022

	2022 \$	2021 \$
<u>INCOME</u>		
SALES		
Membership Fees, Donations	20,855	15,802
Consulting Services	65,060	21,849
Ticket Sales (Events)	-	777
Merchandise	776	-
Total Sales	86,691	38,428
GRANT OPERATING		
Government Grant	-	20,000
JobSaver Subsidy	18,804	-
Other Grants	50,500	44,500
Total Grants Operating	69,304	64,500
DONATIONS & SPONSORSHIP		
Sponsorship	3,000	7,500
Conference Income	23,183	-
Total Donations & Sponsorship	26,183	7,500
OTHER INCOME		
Interest Received	138	96
Cash Flow Boost	-	10,000
Job Keeper Subsidy	-	12,000
Total Other Income	138	22,096
TOTAL INCOME	182,316	132,524

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

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AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

INCOME AND EXPENDITURE STATEMENT FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022

	2022	2021
	\$	\$
<u>EXPENDITURE</u>		
Accounting & Bookkeeping	753	658
Chapter Expenses	1,345	502
Community and Social Gifting	1,164	5,967
Consultants Fees	49,352	8,627
Event Catering	360	-
Event Registration	1,227	-
General Expenses	-	79
Office Expenses	-	8
Printing, Stationery & Postage	422	13
Professional Fees	-	3,225
Promotional Merchandise and Collateral	2,990	2,108
Subscriptions	1,851	1,142
Superannuation Contributions	3,575	5,194
SupporterHub / Stripe Fees	296	-
Travelling Expenses	3,859	20
Wages	34,266	54,675
Website Domain and Plug in Expenses	27	15
Website Hosting	242	1,320
Website Support	-	649
Workcare Insurance	421	334
TOTAL EXPENDITURE	102,150	84,536
 Profit before income tax	 80,166	 47,988

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

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AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

**INCOME AND EXPENDITURE STATEMENT
FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022**

	2022 \$	2021 \$
Profit for the year	80,166	47,988
Retained earnings at the beginning of the financial year	102,988	55,000
Retained earnings at the end of the financial year	183,154	102,988

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report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

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AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

BALANCE SHEET AS AT 30 JUNE 2022

	Note	2022 \$	2021 \$
ASSETS			
CURRENT ASSETS			
Cash and cash equivalents	3	140,702	103,390
Trade and other receivables	4	47,234	-
TOTAL CURRENT ASSETS		187,936	103,390
NON-CURRENT ASSETS			
Property, plant and equipment	5	2,055	2,055
TOTAL NON-CURRENT ASSETS		2,055	2,055
TOTAL ASSETS		189,991	105,445
LIABILITIES			
CURRENT LIABILITIES			
Trade and other payables	6	5,847	1,276
Superannuation Payable		990	1,003
Wages Payable - Payroll		-	178
TOTAL CURRENT LIABILITIES		6,837	2,457
TOTAL LIABILITIES		6,837	2,457
NET ASSETS		183,154	102,988
MEMBERS' FUNDS			
Capital Reserve	7	183,154	102,988
TOTAL MEMBERS' FUNDS		183,154	102,988

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

**CASH FLOW STATEMENT – DIRECT METHOD
FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022**

	2022	2021
	\$	\$
CASH FLOWS FROM OPERATING ACTIVITIES		
Receipts from customers	22,436	15,802.
Payments to suppliers and employees	(37,840)	(59,869)
Cash Receipts from other operating activities	118,903	116,722
Cash Payments from other operating activities	<u>(65,626)</u>	<u>(24,667)</u>
Net cash provided by operating activities	<u>37,873</u>	<u>47,988</u>
CASH FLOWS FROM FINANCING ACTIVITIES		
Other Activities	<u>(561)</u>	<u>(368)</u>
Net cash provided by (used in) financing activities	<u>(561)</u>	<u>(368)</u>
Net increase in cash held	37,312	47,620
Cash at beginning of financial year	103,390	55,770
Cash at end of financial year	<u>140,702</u>	<u>103,3905</u>

The accompanying notes form part of these financial statements.
These statements should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022

The financial statements cover Australian Citizen Science Association as an individual entity. Australian Citizen Science Association is a not for profit Association incorporated in ACT under the Associations Incorporation Act 1991.

The functional and presentation currency of Australian Citizen Science Association is Australian dollars.

Comparatives are consistent with prior years, unless otherwise stated.

1 Basis of Preparation

In the opinion of the Committee of Management, the Association is not a reporting entity since there are unlikely to exist users of the financial report who are not able to command the preparation of reports tailored so as to satisfy specifically all of their information needs. These special purpose financial statements have been prepared to meet the reporting requirements of the Act.

The financial statements have been prepared in accordance with the recognition and measurement requirements of the Australian Accounting Standards and Accounting Interpretations, and the disclosure requirements of AASB 101 Presentation of Financial Statements, AASB 107 Statement of Cash Flows, AASB 108 Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors and AASB 1054 Australian Additional Disclosures.

The financial statements have been prepared on an accruals basis and are based on historical costs modified, where applicable, by the measurement at fair value of selected non-current assets, financial assets and financial liabilities.

Significant accounting policies adopted in the preparation of these financial statements are presented below and are consistent with prior reporting periods unless otherwise stated.

The following significant accounting policies, which are consistent with the previous period unless stated otherwise, have been adopted in the preparation of this financial report.

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

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AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022

2 Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Plant and Equipment

Each class of plant and equipment is carried at cost less, where applicable, any accumulated depreciation and impairment.

At the end of each annual reporting period, the depreciation method, useful life and residual value of each asset is reviewed. Any revisions are accounted for prospectively as a change in estimate.

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

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AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022

Impairment of Non-Financial Assets

At the end of each reporting period the association determines whether there is an evidence of an impairment indicator for non-financial assets.

Where this indicator exists and regardless for goodwill, indefinite life intangible assets and intangible assets not yet available for use, the recoverable amount of the asset is estimated.

Where assets do not operate independently of other assets, the recoverable amount of the relevant cash-generating unit (CGU) is estimated.

The recoverable amount of an asset or CGU is the higher of the fair value less costs of disposal and the value in use. Value in use is the present value of the future cash flows expected to be derived from an asset or cash-generating unit.

Where the recoverable amount is less than the carrying amount, an impairment loss is recognised in profit or loss.

Reversal indicators are considered in subsequent periods for all assets which have suffered an impairment loss , except for goodwill.

Income Tax

The association is a not-for-profit organisation and is exempt from income tax under section 50-45 of the Income Tax Assessment Act 1997.

Cash and Cash Equivalents

Cash and cash equivalents comprises cash on hand, demand deposits and short term investments which are readily convertible to known amounts of cash and which are subject to an insignificant risk of change in value.

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

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AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022

Revenue and Other Income

Revenue is recognised when the amount of the revenue can be measured reliably, it is probable that economic benefits associated with the transaction will flow to the association and specific criteria relating to the type of revenue as noted below, has been satisfied.

Revenue is measured at the fair value of the consideration received or receivable and is presented net of returns, discounts and rebates.

Sale of goods

Revenue from the sale of goods is recognised at the point of delivery as this corresponds to the transfer of significant risks and rewards of ownership of the goods and the cessation of all involvement in those goods.

Interest revenue

Interest revenue is recognised using the effective interest rate method.

Goods and Services Tax (GST)

Revenue, expenses and assets are recognised net of the amount of goods and services tax (GST), except where the amount of GST incurred is not recoverable from the Australian Taxation Office (ATO).

Receivables and payables are stated inclusive of GST.

Cash flows in the cash flow statement are included on a gross basis and the GST component of cash flows arising from investing or financing activities which is recoverable from, or payable to, the taxation authority is classified as operating cash flows.

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

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AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

**NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022**

	2022	2021
	\$	\$
3 Cash and Cash Equivalents		
Community Access Account	140,702	103,390
4 Trade and Other Receivables		
Current		
Trade Debtors	47,234	-
5 Property, plant and equipment		
Computer Equipment	2,055	2,055
Total Plant and Equipment	2,055	2,055
Total Property, Plant and Equipment	2,055	2,055
6 Accounts Payable and Other Payables		
Current		
PAYG Withholding Payable	906	1,276
Tax Clearing Account	4,941	-
	5,847	1,276

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

NOTES TO THE FINANCIAL STATEMENTS FOR THE YEAR ENDED 30 JUNE 2022

	2022	2021
	\$	\$
7 Members' Funds		
Retained earnings at the beginning of the financial year	102,988	55,000
Net profit attributable to the association	<u>80,166</u>	<u>47,988</u>
Retained earnings at the end of the financial year	<u>183,154</u>	<u>102,988</u>

8 Statutory Information

The registered office of the association is:
c/o Faculty of Science, Partner Engagement and Outreach
Room 231, Level 2 Carlaw Building F07
University of Sydney
Sydney 2006, Australia

These notes should be read in conjunction with the attached compilation
report of J & M Accountants & Business Advisors.

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AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

STATEMENT BY MEMBERS OF THE COMMITTEE

The committee has determined that the association is not a reporting entity and that this special purpose financial report should be prepared in accordance with the accounting policies outlined in Note 2 to the financial statements.

In the opinion of the committee the financial report :

1. Presents a true and fair view of the financial position of Australian Citizen Science Association as at 30 June 2022 and its performance for the year ended on that date.
2. At the date of this statement, there are reasonable grounds to believe that Australian Citizen Science Association will be able to pay its debts as and when they fall due.

This statement is made in accordance with a resolution of the Committee and is signed for and on behalf of the Committee by:

Chair:

Annette Lane

Dated: 11/11/2022

Treasurer:

Peter Runcie

Dated: 11/11/2022

COMPILATION REPORT TO AUSTRALIAN CITIZEN SCIENCE ASSOCIATION

We have compiled the accompanying special purpose financial statements of Australian Citizen Science Association which comprise the balance sheet as at 30 June 2022, profit and loss statement and cash flow statement for the year then ended, a summary of significant accounting policies and other explanatory notes. The specific purpose for which the special purpose financial statements have been prepared is set out in the notes to the accounts.

The responsibility of the committee of management

The Committee of Management of Australian Citizen Science Association is solely responsible for the information contained in the special purpose financial statements, the reliability, accuracy and completeness of the information and for the determination that the basis of accounting used is appropriate to meet their needs and for the purpose that the financial statements were prepared.

Our responsibility

On the basis of the information provided by the committee of management we have compiled the accompanying special purpose financial statements in accordance with the basis of accounting as described in the notes to the financial statements and APES 315: Compilation of Financial Information.

We have applied professional expertise in accounting and financial reporting to compile these financial statements in accordance with the basis of accounting described in the notes to the financial statements. We have complied with the relevant ethical requirements of APES 110 Code of Ethics for Professional Accountants.

Assurance Disclaimer

Since a compilation engagement is not an assurance engagement, we are not required to verify the reliability, accuracy or completeness of the information provided to us by management to compile these financial statements. Accordingly, we do not express an audit opinion or a review conclusion on these financial statements.

The special purpose financial statements were compiled exclusively for the benefit of the committee of management who are responsible for the reliability, accuracy and completeness of the information used to compile them. We do not accept responsibility to any other person for the contents of the special purpose financial statements.

Name of Firm: J & M Accountants & Business Advisors
Certified Practising Accountants

Name of Partner:

Janine Brunhead

Address:

Level 6, 34 Queen St MELBOURNE VIC 3000

Dated this 10th day of November 2022